

interstore

D2.6 – LEGACY SYSTEMS PROTOCOL CONVERTER – FINAL VERSION

WP2 – Open-source Interoperability Toolkit

T2.2 – Legacy systems protocol converter

Submission date: 31 Mar 2025 (Final version – extended initial version
D2.2, submitted on 31 Mar 2024)

Project Acronym	INTERSTORE
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01
Grant Agreement N°	101096511
Project Start Date	01-01-2023
Project End Date	31-12-2025
Duration	36 months

INFORMATION

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Status	Final	

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

CO	Confidential	
CL	Classified	
PU	Public	X

VERSIONS

Date	Version	Comment
18. 9. 2024	0.1	Additions and improvements from D2.2
15. 10. 2024	0.2	Additions and improvements
24. 11. 2024	0.3	Additions and improvements
17. 12. 2025	0.4	Additions and improvements
22. 1. 2025	0.5	Additions and improvements
28. 2. 2025	0.6	Additions and improvements
4. 3. 2025	0.7	Additions and improvements
5. 3. 2025	0.9	Final version for internal review
25. 3. 2025	1.0	Final version

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

InterSTORE is a EU-funded project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N. 101096511.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

API	Application Programming Interface
EMS	Energy Management System
GPL	General Public License
HESS	Hybrid Energy Storage Systems
JAR	Java ARchive
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JVM	Java Virtual Machine
JWT	JSON web token
LPC	Legacy Protocol Converter
LTS	Long Term Support
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
msg	Message
NATS	Neural Autonomic Transport System
QoS	Quality of Service
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TLS	Transport Layer Security
XML	Extensible Markup Language
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

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1 Introduction

The Legacy Protocol Converter, initially developed within the Horizon Europe Interstore project, acts as a middleware, allowing devices that use different communication protocols to exchange data with EMS systems that use the IEEE2030.5 standard. IEEE 2030.5 is a standard for communications between the smart grid and consumers.

Legacy Protocol Converter supports:

- **IEEE2030.5 communication:** This is the primary function of the Legacy Protocol Converter. It can handle IEEE2030.5 messages in both JSON and XML formats.
- **Next-generation NATS messaging:** This is a new messaging protocol that the converter uses to communicate with devices and EMS systems. It is designed to be more efficient and scalable than traditional protocols like REST over HTTP.
- **MQTT and Modbus protocols:** These are common protocols used by many devices. The Legacy Protocol Converter can translate messages from these protocols into the IEEE2030.5 format for use with EMS systems.

Key features of Legacy Protocol Converter:

- **Built-in transformation framework:** This framework allows users to define how incoming messages should be transformed into the outgoing IEEE2030.5 format. This is important because different devices and systems may use different message formats.
- **Configuration file:** The converter uses a configuration file to specify connection details for NATS, MQTT, and Modbus devices. Users can also define transformations within the configuration file.
- **Flexibility:** The converter can support multiple transformations, each with different incoming and outgoing connections, message formats, and structures. This allows for a high degree of flexibility in how the converter is used.

The Legacy Protocol Converter can be deployed and run using:

- A Docker container.
 - Pre-built Docker images are available on Docker Hub,
 - A custom Docker image can be built.
- Using a Java JAR file and execute it on any computer with OpenJDK Java Runtime Environment.
- Compile and build the project out of source code.
- It is possible to integrate LPC in custom projects by including packages.

LPC can be executed on-premise or in the cloud. It supports a variety of environments, including Kubernetes, Docker and classical virtual machines, as well as bare-metal.

Overall, the Legacy Protocol Converter is a tool for enabling communication between devices and EMS systems that use different communication protocols. It supports the latest IEEE2030.5 standard and provides a flexible and efficient way to translate messages between different protocols.

The document is the extension of D2.2, which has been the initial version of this document. Since the initial version, there have been several improvements and optimizations to the LPC, including logging support, IEEE 2030.5 compliance checking, improved serialization, performance and error handling. Also, a web user interface, the LPC Generator User Interface has been developed to simplify the configuration and make it more user friendly.

2 Software Architecture and Usage Scenarios

Legacy Protocol Converter consists of a transformation module in the package *si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformation*, where classes for handling transformations are defined.

Figure 1: Legacy Protocol Converter package diagram

Figure 1: Legacy Protocol Converter package diagram shows the overall package structure. On the figure you can see the packages, which are used within the interoperability common and legacy protocol converter. Figure 1 also shows the submodules of the LPC and interoperability common modules.

For handling configuration files, configuration framework is used, where users can define parameters of connections and transformations. Configuration can be defined in:

- A configuration file using YAML syntax.
- Through environment variables.

The configuration file is handled in the package *si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.models*. For handling whole configuration file, *YamlTransformationsModel* is used. There is a list of connections *YamlConnectionModel* and a list of transformations *YamlTransformationModel*.

Depending on the type of connections defined in the configuration file, appropriate client is initiated to communicate with devices/servers. Each client has different parameters necessary to make a connection. For connection, clients that are used are from project interoperability-common with package for:

- Modbus *si.sunesis.interoperability.modbus*,
- MQTT *si.sunesis.interoperability.mqtt* and
- NATS *si.sunesis.interoperability.nats*.

Each client implements the same interface, so the user does not have to know which client is which as they each handle message according to their respective protocol.

For each defined transformation, Legacy Protocol Converter will subscribe using the connections listed in the incoming connections to the incoming topic. When the LPC receives the message, it transforms the message according to the defined structure and mapping in the outgoing message and vice-versa for receiving messages from outgoing connections.

For handling all of the logic behind transformations, class *TransformationHandler* in the package *si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation* is built with this purpose. It handles subscribing and publishing messages, requesting messages from Modbus and transforming between structures and formats.

In the package *si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers* are two different mapper classes, one for XML messages and one for JSON messages. That is because they each handle mappings depending on the format using respective libraries.

Examples can be seen in the chapter 4.

3 Languages, Technologies and Tools

Legacy Protocol Converter is developed in Java. Java 17 or higher is required for Legacy Protocol Converter, with plans to upgrade to Java 21 in the future releases.

Legacy Protocol Converter is developed using microservice architecture. The source code is based on Java Microprofile specification. KumuluzEE framework is used for the project as it is open-source lightweight framework for microservices and offers support for cloud-native applications.

KumuluzEE Maven dependencies that are used, are:

- KumuluzEE BOM, version 4.1.0
- KumuluzEE Core, version 4.1.0
- KumuluzEE Servlet Jetty, version 4.1.0
- KumuluzEE CDI Weld, version 4.1.0
- KumuluzEE Logs, version 1.4.6

The Legacy Protocol Converter is also using the common package from the *si.sunesis interoperability.common* group for managing connections with NATS, MQTT and Modbus.

Maven dependencies in the common package are:

- KumuluzEE BOM, version 4.1.0
- KumuluzEE MicroProfile 3.3, version 4.1.0
- KumuluzEE Logs, version 1.4.6
- Lombok, version 1.8.36
- NATS – Java Client, version 2.20.4
- HiveMQ – MQTT Client, version 1.3.4
- JLibModbus, version 1.2.9.11

Other Maven dependencies are:

- Jakarta XML Bind API, version 4.0.2
- Jaxb-impl, version 4.0.5

4 Data Models and Transformations

Data Models are handled depending on format of the message. XML messages are handled using Java's built-in methods in the package `java.xml`. JSON messages are handled with the help of Jackson JSON parser.

Code snippet for generating JSON:

```
JsonNode jsonNode = new ObjectMapper().readTree(message);
```

Code snippet for generating XML:

```
DocumentBuilderFactory factory = DocumentBuilderFactory.newInstance();

factory.setFeature(XMLConstants.FEATURE_SECURE_PROCESSING, true);
factory.setFeature("http://apache.org/xml/features/disallow-doctype-decl", true);
factory.setXIncludeAware(false);
factory.setNamespaceAware(false);

DocumentBuilder builder = factory.newDocumentBuilder();
InputStream inputStream = new InputSource(new
java.io.StringReader(xmlString));
Document document = builder.parse(message);
```

Each transformation generates XML or JSON message depending on the specified format in the configuration of the transformation.

```
connections:
-
-
transformations:
- name: string
  description: string
  validate-ieee2030-5: true/false
  connections:
    incoming-connection:
      -
      -
    incoming-topic: string
    incoming-format: XML/JSON
    outgoing-connection:
      -
      -
    outgoing-topic: string
    outgoing-format: XML/JSON
  to-outgoing:
    retry-count: integer
    topic: string
    message: string
  to-incoming:
    retry-count: integer
    to-topic: string
    message: string
```



```

or
to-incoming:
  retry-count: integer
  modbus-function-code: integer
  modbus-device-id: integer
  endianness: big/little
  modbus-registers:
    - register-address: integer
      path: string
      type: int8/int16/int32/int64/float32/float64
      pattern: string
      values: array
interval-request:
  interval: integer
  request:
    modbus-function-code: integer
    modbus-device-id: integer
    endianness: big/little
    modbus-registers:
      - register-address: integer
        path: string
        type: int8/int16/int32/int64/float32/float64
        pattern: string
        values: array
or
request:
  to-topic: string
  reply-from-topic: string
  message: string

```

Options:

- **name:** Short name of the transformation
- **description:** Description of the transformation
- **validate-ieee2030-5:** Validates messages for correct JSON or XML structure and if the message is IEEE2030.5 compliant
- **connections**
 - **incoming-connection:** List of connection names, these connections will be used for sending/receiving the data from clients. If using Modbus, only Modbus connections must be listed here. Must match the name in the connections.
 - **incoming-topic:** On which topic MQTT/NATS client will send the incoming messages or listen for messages from devices. If using Modbus, this must be omitted.
 - **incoming-format:** Format of the incoming messages.
 - **outgoing-connection:** List of connection names, these connections will be used for sending/receiving the data from server. Must match the name in the connections.
 - **outgoing-topic:** On which topic MQTT/NATS client will send the outgoing messages or listen for message from server.
 - **connections.outgoing-format:** Format of the outgoing messages.
- **to-outgoing:** Structure of the outgoing message with defined mappings.
 - **to-outgoing.retry-count:** Number of retries for sending the message.

- to-outgoing.to-topic: Topic on which the message will be sent.
- message: Message with mappings that will be sent to the specified topic.
- to-incoming: Structure of the incoming message with defined options.
 - retry-count: Number of retries for sending the message.
 - to-topic: Topic on which the message will be sent.
 - message: Message with mappings that will be sent to the specified topic.
 - modbus-function-code: Function code for reading/writing data from/to Modbus device.
 - modbus-device-id: Client id of the Modbus device.
 - endianness: Endianness of the data, big or little. Default value is little.
 - modbus-registers: List of definitions of modbus registers used for writing/reading the data.
- interval-request: Structure of the interval request with defined options.
 - interval: Interval in milliseconds for sending the request.
 - request: Structure of the request with defined mappings and topic.
 - to-topic: Topic on which the message will be sent.
 - reply-from-topic: Topic from which the reply will be received.
 - message: Message with mappings that will be sent to the specified topic.
 - modbus-function-code: Function code for reading/writing data from/to Modbus device.
 - modbus-device-id: Client id of the Modbus device.
 - endianness: Endianness of the data, big or little. Default value is little.
 - modbus-registers: List of definitions of modbus registers used for writing/reading the data.

4.1 Mapping definitions

Transforming messages from one structure to another is done with the help of a mapper. Each mapper has the following variables that are configurable:

- Type
- Path
- Pattern
- Values

Type specifies the type to which value must be converted to. Possible values are: *integer*, *float*, *double*, *date*, *datetime* and *string*. When using Modbus, number of bits is required, so *integer8* (or *int8*), *int16*, *int32*, *int64*, *uint8*, *uint16*, *uint32*, *uint64* and also *float32* and *float64*; *int64* is converted to long and *float64* is converted to double. *date* and *datetime* are converted to long representing the number of milliseconds since January 1, 1970, 00:00:00 GMT.

Path specifies path to the value that will be used in new message structure. For XML/JSON this is done using XPath or JSON Pointer (e.g. `/OutgoingEvent/currentStatus`). For Modbus messages, register address must be provided.

Pattern is needed only when type is *datetime* or *date* as it specifies the format of the provided temporal value at path.

Values is needed only when value must be converted to the index of an array or index to some value from the array.

For easier explanation of options, here are the examples.

4.1.1 Transforming from JSON to XML

This example showcases transformation of IncomingEvent in JSON format to IEEE2030.5 Event in XML format.

JSON IncomingEvent
<pre>{ "datetime": "28-08-2023 12:00:35", "status": "active", "start": "28-08-2023", "duration": 900 }</pre>
XML IEEE2030.5 Event
<pre><Event> <creationTime>1702909917932</creationTime> <EventStatus> <currentStatus>1</currentStatus> <dateTime>1693216835000</dateTime> <potentiallySuperseded> False </potentiallySuperseded> </EventStatus> <interval> <duration>900</duration> <start>1693216835000</start> </interval> </Event></pre>

Example of the configuration for this transformation:

<pre>connections: - name: NATS-connection type: NATS host: nats://localhost port: 4222 reconnect: true - name: MQTT-connection type: MQTT ssl: default: true host: localhost port: 8883 username: username password: password transformations: - name: JSON IncomingEvent to XML IEEE2030.5 Event description: Example showing transformation of messages from JSON to XML validate-ieee2030-5: false connections: incoming-connection: - MQTT-connection incoming-topic: topic1 incoming-format: JSON outgoing-connection:</pre>

```

- NATS-connection
  outgoing-topic: event/listen
  outgoing-format: XML
to-outgoing:
  to-topic: event/send
  message: '<Event>
    <creationTime>$timestamp</creationTime>
    <EventStatus>
      <currentStatus>
        <lpc:mapping>
          <path type="integer">/status</path>
          <values>["scheduled", "active", "cancelled", "cancelled_with_r", "superseded"]</values>
        </lpc:mapping>
      </currentStatus>
      <dateTime>
        <lpc:mapping>
          <path type="datetime">datetime</path>
          <pattern>dd-MM-yyyy HH:mm:ss</pattern>
        </lpc:mapping>
      </dateTime>
      <potentiallySuperseded>>false</potentiallySuperseded>
    </EventStatus>
    <interval>
      <duration>
        <lpc:mapping>
          <path type="integer">duration</path>
        </lpc:mapping>
      </duration>
      <start>
        <lpc:mapping>
          <path type="date">/start</path>
          <pattern>dd-MM-yyyy</pattern>
        </lpc:mapping>
      </start>
    </interval>
  </Event>
  '

```

With this transformation we specify that the MQTT-connection will subscribe to topic *topic/* and LPC will transform the message to XML structure, and it will send the transformed message using NATS-connection to topic *event/send*.

We can see that the mapping is done with the help of XML tag *<lpc:mapping>*.

For setting the value of *OutgoingEvent/currentStatus*, we are converting value "active" to integer 1. Because the *IncomingEvent/status* is string, and we have provided values options, this means we will map to the integer based on which index is the value of *IncomingEvent/status*. So "active" maps to 1.

For setting the value of *OutgoingEvent/datetime*, we are converting from *datetime* to *long*. Because *type* is *datetime*, we need to provide the pattern of the incoming value, so LPC know how to parse the value, hence *dd-MM-yyyy HH:mm:ss*. Also note that the leading / is not

needed. Same applies for setting the value of *OutgoingEvent/interval/start*, but here we are using *date*.

For setting the value of *OutgoingEvent/interval/duration* we just need to specify *type*, because mapping is done 1 on 1.

There is also reserved keyword *\$timestamp* which is used to set the value of *OutgoingEvent/creationTime* to the current time in milliseconds.

5 Configuration

General format of the configuration file is following:

```
logging:
  configuration-name:
  status:
  appenders:
    -
    -
  loggers:
    -
    -
  root-logger:
    level:
    appender-refs:
      -
      -
connections:
  -
  -
registration:
  topic:
  outgoing-connection:
    -
    -
  message:
transformations:
  -
  -
```

Logging, registration, connections and transformation must be defined by the user.

5.1 Logging

The logging configuration provides a flexible and structured way to configure logging in your application. Below is a detailed description of the configuration possibilities for the logging section.

5.1.1 Quick logging configuration

Quick logging configuration is to just leave logging configuration empty. The default configuration will be used. For changing the logging level at the runtime or when launching the LPC using Docker set the environment variable `ROOT_LOG_LEVEL` or `LOG_LEVEL` to the desired level. `ROOT_LOG_LEVEL` will change the logging level for the root logger and `LOG_LEVEL` will change the logging level for the logger *si.sunesis.interoperability*.

Possible logging levels are:

ALL, TRACE, DEBUG, INFO, WARN, ERROR, FATAL, OFF.

With ALL being the lowest and OFF being the highest level.

For production, we recommend using ERROR or higher level.

Default logging configuration is the following:


```

logging:
  configuration-name: lpc
  status: info
  appenders:
    - type: console
      name: console
      target: SYSTEM_OUT
      pattern: "%d %p %logger{36} - %msg%n"
    - type: RollingFile
      name: file_lpc
      fileName: lpc.log
      filePattern: lpc-%d{yyyy-MM-dd}.log
      pattern: "%d %p %logger{36} - %msg%n"
      policies:
        - type: TimeBasedTriggeringPolicy
          interval: 1
          modulate: false
      default-rollover-strategy:
        type: Delete
        deleteFilePattern: "lpc-*.log"
        deleteAge: 1m
  root-logger:
    level: info
    appender-refs:
      - ref: console
        level: info
  loggers:
    - name: si.sunesis.interoperability
      level: debug
      appender-refs:
        - ref: file_lpc
          level: debug

```

5.1.2 Detailed logging configuration

1. General configuration:
 - **configuration-name:** This is the name of the logging configuration. By default, it is set to "lpc". You can change this to any string value to identify the configuration.
 - **status:** This sets the overall status of the logging configuration. It can be set to either "debug" or "info". The default value is "info".
2. Appenders: Appenders define where the log messages will be output (e.g., console, file, etc.).
 - **name:** A unique name for the appender.
 - **type:** The type of appender (e.g., Console, File, RollingFile, etc.).
 - **target:** The target for the appender (e.g., System.out, System.err for console appenders).
 - **fileName:** The name of the file where logs will be written (applicable for file-based appenders).
 - **filePattern:** The pattern for the file name, especially useful for rolling file appenders.
 - **pattern:** The format of the log messages. The default pattern is "%d %p -- %c -- %marker %m %X %ex %n".

- policies: A list of policies that determine when the log file should roll over (e.g., based on time, size, etc.).
 - type: The type of triggering policy (e.g., TimeBasedTriggeringPolicy, SizeBasedTriggeringPolicy, CronBasedTriggeringPolicy and OnStartupTriggeringPolicy).
 - cron: A cron expression for cron-based rollover.
 - size: The maximum size of the log file before it rolls over for size-based triggering.
 - minSize: The minimum size of the log file before it rolls over for on startup triggering.
 - interval: The interval for time-based rollover.
 - modulate: Whether to modulate the interval for time-based rollover.
 - default-rollover-strategy: Configuration for the rollover strategy.
 - type: The type of rollover strategy.
 - deleteFilePattern: The pattern for files to delete during rollover.
 - deleteAge: The age of files to delete during rollover.
3. **Loggers:** Loggers are used to control the logging level and the appenders that will be used for specific parts of your application.
- name: The name of the logger, typically corresponding to a package or class name.
 - level: The logging level for the logger (e.g., info, debug, error). The default is "info".
 - appender-refs: A list of appender references that this logger will use.
 - ref: The name of the appender to reference.
 - level: The logging level for the appender reference. The default is "info".
4. **Root logger:** The root logger is the default logger that will be used if no other logger is specified.
- level: The logging level for the root logger. The default is "info".
 - appender-refs: A list of appender references that the root logger will use.
 - ref: The name of the appender to reference.
 - level: The logging level for the appender reference. The default is "info".

5.2 Connections

Each incoming/outgoing connection must be configured in the list of connections, so the LPC knows how to connect accordingly.

Possible options for each connection are following:


```

connections:
  - name: string
    type: NATS/MQTT/Modbus
    host: string
    port: integer
    ssl:
      default: true/false
    username: string
    password: string
    reconnect: true/false
    device: string
    baud-rate: integer
    data-bits: integer
    parity: none/even/odd/space/mark
    stop-bits: integer
transformations:
  - ...

```

Name and type are required keys.

5.2.1 NATS

Currently supported parameters for connection with NATS are host, port, username, password and reconnect.

Example of configuration for NATS:

```

connections:
  - name: NATS-connection
    type: NATS
    host: nats://localhost
    port: 4222
    username: userTest
    password: testUser
    reconnect: true
transformations:
  - ...

```

5.2.2 MQTT

Currently supported parameters for connection with NATS are host, port, ssl, username, password and reconnect.

Example of configuration for MQTT:

```

connections:
  - name: MQTT-connection
    type: MQTT
    host: localhost
    port: 8883
    ssl:
      default: true
    username: userTest
    password: testUser
    reconnect: false

```



```
transformations:
-...
```

5.2.3 Modbus

Configuration for Modbus depends on connection type, LPC supports serial connection or TCP connection. For TCP connection parameters host and port are required. For serial connection parameter device is required, optional parameters are baud-rate, data-bits, parity and stop-bits. Modbus connection cannot be used as an outgoing connection, because it is a request-reply protocol.

Example of configuration for serial Modbus connection:

```
connections:
- name: Modbus-connection
  type: Modbus
  device: /dev/ttymx2
  baud-rate: 115200
  data-bits: 8
  parity: none
transformations:
-...
```

Example of configuration for TCP Modbus connection:

```
connections:
- name: Modbus-connection
  type: Modbus
  host: localhost
  port: 502
transformations:
-...
```

5.3 Registration

Registration is optional and provides support for registering the LPC by specified connections. It is designed to send a message once to the specified topic when the LPC is started.

Possible options are:

```
registration:
  topic: string
  outgoing-connection:
  -
  -
  message: string
```

- **topic:** Topic on which the registration message will be sent.
- **outgoing-connection:** List of connection names, this connections will be used for sending registration message to server. Must match the name in the connections.
- **message:** Message that will be sent to the specified topic.

6 LPC Generator User Interface

Purpose of LPC Generator is generation of configuration files for LPC. It is designed to provide more straightforward and simplified process of configuring parameters for running LPC. It is accessible here: <https://sunesis.si/interstore/lpc/>

LPC Generator guides the user through the configuration steps and provides information about the errors in the configuration. Through LPC Generator User Interface, the user can specify all relevant parameters for the configuration of the LPC in a user-friendly way. The LPC Generator will create the configuration file and the user can download it and use it in its own deployment of LPC.

On Figure 2 we can see the initial screen, where a user can choose an existing configuration file or create a new LPC configuration file.

Figure 2: Landing page of LPC Generator

Figure 3 shows the configuration of connections. Here the user specifies the names and parameters of all connections that he will use with the LPC. These include NATS, MQTT, ModBus and other connections. The user also needs to specify the details of each connection, such as IP address or URL, port, username, password and other details.

Figure 3: Configuration of Connections

Figures 4 and 5 show the actual configuration of transformations. The LPC Generator guides us through the steps and the user has to enter all the relevant information about the incoming and outgoing transformations and specify the parameters. On the figures we can see a sample configuration from custom MQTT payload to IEEE 2030.5 XML based Event structure.

Figure 4: Configuration of Transformations

Figure 5: Configuration of Transformations

Figure 6 shows the final step, where we can download the configuration file and use it with our LPC deployment.

Figure 6: Downloading the configuration file

7 Deployment and usage

For building the code, Maven is needed as this is a Maven project. There are two ways this project can be deployed, using JAR, or using Docker container.

When deploying the application, users must provide path to the configuration folder. Default configuration path is: *./conf*

7.1.1 JAR

JAR is generated by running Maven command:

```
mvn clean package
```

This will build all modules and once completed the build archives will be in the modules respected target folder.

Legacy Protocol Converter can be started from JAR using Uber-Jar:

```
java -jar -DCONFIGURATION=/path/to/config target/${project.build.finalName}.jar
```

7.1.2 Docker

Docker container is built using the command:

```
docker build -t lpc:latest .
```

and then started using the command:

```
docker run -v /path/to/config:/app/conf lpc:latest
```

When starting the application using Docker, users must mount the configuration folder, so that the Legacy Protocol Converter can use the configurations defined by the user.

8 Open-source access on GitHub

The source code for the Client/Server, Legacy protocol converter and testing procedures will be available on GitHub. We have created a repository: <https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore>

Within the repository there are currently four projects:

- Interoperable client/server for distributed energy storage
- Legacy system protocol converter
- Testing procedures and software tools
- Interoperable data spaces framework

The LPC source code can be found here: <https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore/Legacy-Protocol-Converter>

Within the repository, detailed description of the project, source code and build and run instructions is given.

Figure 7: Open-source repository on GitHub.

9 Docker image available on Docker Hub

A pre-built version of Docker image is publicly available on Docker Hub. This enables easy access to Docker images and their updates.

Docker image is available here: <https://hub.docker.com/r/interstore/legacy-protocol-converter>

Within the Docker Hub, detailed description and instructions for using Docker image are posted.

The screenshot shows the Docker Hub page for the image 'interstore/legacy-protocol-converter'. The page includes a search bar, a navigation menu, and a main content area. The main content area features a 3D cube icon, the image name, and a description: 'Legacy Protocol Converter is a framework designed to convert messages from one protocol to another.' Below this, there are sections for 'Running the container' and 'Configuration'. The 'Running the container' section includes a terminal command: `docker run -v /path/to/config:/app/conf legacy-protocol-converter:latest`. The 'Configuration' section is currently empty. On the right side, there is a 'Docker Pull Command' section with a text box containing `docker pull interstore/legacy-p` and a 'Copy' button. The page also shows 'Pulls 4' and a 'Sign up' button.

Figure 8: Docker image registry on Docker Hub.

10 Conclusion

In this specification, we have provided overview of architecture and configuration for the Legacy Protocol Converter. This document is the extension of D2.2, which has been the initial version of the Legacy Systems Protocol Converter, submitted in M18 of the project. This document provides a description of the software architecture, its components, packages and classes. It also provides a list of technologies used.

Furthermore, this document provides a detailed description of the configuration, parameters, and transformation engine to enable seamless protocol transformation between ModBus, MQTT and IEEE2030.5 using NATS in either XML or JSON representation. Legacy protocol converter provides support for ModBus and MQTT and provides a transformation and configuration framework, which allows simple and fully configurable transformation of messages between ModBus, MQTT, NATS, IEEE2030.5 XML and JSON messages.

LPC provides full support for next generation NATS messaging as a communication protocol between devices and EMS systems. This enables message-driven, loosely coupled and scalable communication platform, which provides out-of-the-box support for computer cloud environments.

Legacy protocol converter follows the microservice architecture. It has been implemented in Java using open source OpenJDK using Java Microprofile and KumuluzEE framework. It is provided as Docker container, pre-built Java JAR archive, or custom-built configuration for specific use cases. All software artifacts are available on GitHub and Docker Hub.

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